

INFLUENCE OF TEACHERS' REWARD SYSTEM ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF NASARAWA SOUTH SENATORIAL ZONE, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study assessed “Influence of Teachers' Reward System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.” The focus of the study was to assess Star Chart, Point System, two research questions were raised and two hypotheses framed and tested at 0.05 level of significance. All the indices/variables of the study have been conceptualized. Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of 1350 (85 principals and 1265 teachers). For the sample size; 818 (67 principals and 751 teachers) from the population were sampled using Krejcie Morgan and Daryle distribution table of (1970) where (N) size population were assign appropriate sample size (S) number. The questionnaire were developed based on the targeted objectives of the study by the researcher for data collection; the instruments were validated by one expert from Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Nasarawa State, University. The result of the validated instruments yielded 0.79. Data related to the research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation) while chi-square test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the , Star Chart, Point System, , and Student of the Week/Month strategies were found to positively motivate students, foster engagement, and improve learning outcomes. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that, schools should institutionalize structured reward systems (e.g., Star Chart , Point System) and provide teacher training for consistent, equitable implementation. Policymakers should allocate resources for reward materials, digital tools, and monitoring frameworks to sustain motivation.

Keywords: Teachers' Reward System, Students' Academic Achievement

Introduction

Education is the systematic process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and habits through instruction, study, and practical experience. It encompasses formal learning within institutions such as schools, colleges, and universities, as well as informal learning that occurs throughout life. It is a cornerstone of any societal development, shaping individuals' knowledge, skills, and values. Teachers play a critical role in this process, influencing student success and overall educational quality. However, the demanding nature of teaching often goes with teachers' use of different instructional method in a bid to foster academic achievement Abah, & Edeh, (2018). Teachers' use of a reward system involves acknowledging and reinforcing positive behavior and academic achievements in students. By offering system like Star Chart system, Point System, leveling up system and Student of the Week/Month, teachers aim to motivate learning, foster a positive classroom environment, and encourage desired behaviors, ultimately enhancing student engagement and academic achievement. By providing clear goals and associated rewards, teachers can encourage desirable behaviors, enhance student participation, and reinforce

positive academic and social outcomes. A well-designed reward system will help students understand the connection between effort and achievement, promoting a growth mindset and self-discipline. It also allows teachers to tailor motivation strategies to individual student needs, addressing diverse learning styles and challenges. Consistent and fair implementation is crucial to maintaining the system's credibility and effectiveness Adamu, & Garba, (2017). Teachers must balance extrinsic rewards with intrinsic motivation to ensure students remain genuinely interested in learning. Over-reliance on rewards can lead to a dependency on external incentives rather than fostering a love for learning. Therefore, integrating rewards with intrinsic motivators, such as fostering curiosity, providing meaningful feedback, and creating engaging lesson plans, is essential.

The Star Chart system operates similarly, using stars as rewards for good behavior and academic achievements. This system is a behavioral management tool used primarily by teachers in educational settings to reinforce positive behavior and encourage students to meet specific goals or expectations. It operates on the principle of positive reinforcement, where students receive stars, stickers, or other symbols as rewards for demonstrating desired behaviors, such as completing assignments on time, participating in class discussions, or showing kindness to classmates. The system typically involves a chart displayed prominently in the classroom, divided into sections representing different behaviors or tasks. Each time a student exhibits the targeted behavior, they receive a star or sticker on the chart. As students accumulate stars, they may earn rewards, such as privileges, prizes, or recognition Adeyemi, (2016).

The Star Chart system is effective due to its immediate feedback and tangible rewards, reinforcing positive behaviors and motivating students to continue their good actions. It fosters a sense of accomplishment and pride as students see their progress visually represented on the chart. This system is adaptable to individual needs and can be used across various age groups and classroom settings, promoting a positive classroom culture and encouraging self-regulation and responsibility. By enhancing overall student engagement and achievement, it creates a conducive learning environment (Adeyemi, 2016).

Similarly, the point system operates on the same principles, where students earn points for meeting specific goals or displaying desirable behaviors. Points can be accumulated and redeemed for rewards, providing immediate gratification and motivation. The point system is a method of behavior management commonly used in educational settings to encourage positive behavior and discourage negative actions. It operates on the principle of assigning points or credits to individuals based on their behavior or performance. Points are typically awarded for demonstrating desired behaviors, such as completing assignments, participating in class discussions, or helping others, and may be deducted for infractions or undesirable actions. Points can be accumulated over time, and individuals may receive rewards or privileges based on their point totals. Conversely, individuals who consistently engage in negative behavior may face consequences or lose privileges. The point system is effective because it provides clear expectations and consequences, encourages accountability, and offers immediate feedback on behavior. It also allows for the tracking of progress over time, enabling individuals to see their improvement and providing opportunities for intervention or support when needed. This system can be customized to suit the needs of different groups or settings, and it can be combined with other behavior management strategies, such as Leveling up system, to create a comprehensive approach to behavior management Ahmed, & Musa, (2020).

Students' academic achievement refers to students performance and success in educational pursuits, typically measured by grades, test scores, and other academic indicators. It reflects the

extent to which students have mastered the content, skills, and concepts taught in their courses of curriculum. Several factors influence students' academic achievement including Teachers' Reward System. High levels of academic achievement are associated with numerous benefits, including greater opportunities for higher education, improved career prospects, and enhanced socio-economic mobility. Academic success can boost students' self-esteem, confidence, and overall well-being. Any success in students' academic achievement is closely linked to teachers' reward systems, as the effectiveness of educators directly impacts student learning outcomes. A well-designed reward system for teachers can incentivize and recognize behaviors that contribute to improved academic achievement among students Bello, & Ogunleye, (2023).

Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, has been experiencing a concerning decline in academic achievement among its public secondary school students. This downward trend is attributed to various factors, including inadequate teaching resources, inconsistent teaching methods, and a lack of student motivation and engagement. The region's schools often struggle with insufficient funding, leading to overcrowded classrooms, outdated materials, and undertrained teachers, all of which negatively impact the quality of education Hamza (2020). Amid these challenges, there is an urgent need for an effective teaching system that can reverse the falling levels of academic achievement. A promising solution might be the implementation of structured reward systems. These systems, such as the Star Chart system, Point System, leveling-up system, and Student of the Week/Month program, have been shown to significantly boost student motivation and engagement in other endeavors (Aluko & Adeoye, 2021). By recognizing and rewarding positive behaviors and academic accomplishments, these systems can foster a more supportive and encouraging learning environment. Properly applied, reward systems can address the motivational deficits and create a more dynamic classroom atmosphere. This approach requires consistent application and adequate training for teachers to ensure they can effectively implement these tools. By adopting a reward-based teaching system, schools in Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone might potentially improve students' academic achievement. It is to this backdrop that this study seek to examine the influence Teachers' Reward System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Statement of the Problem

Despite the government's efforts to improve educational outcomes in public secondary schools in the Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria, students' academic achievement remains low. The researcher has observed that the ineffective implementation of teachers' reward systems may significantly be a contributing factor. Various reward systems, such as the Privilege Pass system, Star Chart system, Point System, Leveling Up system, and Student of the Week/Month program, have been introduced to motivate students and enhance their performance. However, these systems are not being effectively utilized by teachers. Inconsistencies in application, lack of regular updates, poor record-keeping, and insufficient training or interest among teachers have undermined the potential benefits of these reward systems. Consequently, students remain unmotivated and disengaged, leading to suboptimal academic outcomes. It is on this note that this study seek to examine the influence of a Teachers' Reward System on students' academic achievement in the public secondary schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question:

The following research questions is raised to guide the study:

What is the influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria?

- ii. What is the impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses postulated will be tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

- i. There is no significant influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significant impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design to determine the influence of teachers' reward system on students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design is appropriate for large population studies and allows the researcher to gather data within a short period from a randomly selected portion of the target population (Anikweze, 2013). This design enabled the researcher to describe and examine relationships among variables and to draw inferences from the data collected about the population based on the representative sample. The population of the study comprised all teachers and principals in public secondary schools across the five Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Nasarawa South: Obi, Awe, Keana, Doma, and Lafia. According to records from the Nasarawa State Ministry of Education (2024), the population includes 85 principals and 1,265 teachers, summing up to a total of 1,350 academic staff across 85 schools. The sample size consisted of 818 respondents, made up of 67 principals and 751 teachers drawn from 67 schools. The Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of sample size determination guided the sampling process, and simple random sampling was employed to ensure fairness and reduce bias in selection. A structured questionnaire titled *Questionnaire on the Influence of Teachers' Reward System on Students' Academic Achievement* was used for data collection. The instrument was divided into two sections: Section A gathered demographic information, while Section B contained items based on a modified four-point Likert scale format: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument underwent face and construct validation by an expert in the Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Foundations, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. Suggestions from the expert were implemented, and the final version was approved by the researcher's supervisor. For reliability, a pilot study was conducted using a group of teachers outside the sample population, and Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.77, which was considered acceptable. Questionnaires were administered in person by the researcher and a trained assistant, following ethical procedures and institutional approval. Respondents were given the liberty to seek clarification during the process. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), while hypotheses were

tested using the Chi-square statistical method to determine the association between variables based on observed and expected frequencies.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the influence of teachers’ use of Star Chart system on Students’ Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria?

Table 4.2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of the Influence of Teachers’ Use of Star Chart System on Students’ Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Item No	Item Description	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	Decision
1.	The Star Chart system employed by teachers significantly contributes to enhancing students' academic achievement.	205	524	54	35	3.55	0.63	Strongly Agree
2.	Students perceive that the Star Chart system implemented by teachers effectively motivates them to excel academically.	316	432	30	40	3.52	0.70	Strongly Agree
3.	The Star Chart system positively influences students' engagement in classroom activities and learning.	372	381	28	37	2.77	0.60	Agree
Cluster Mean						3.13		Agree

Table 4.2 shows that items 1-3 had mean scores of 3.55, 3.52, 2.77, with corresponding standard deviations of 0.63, 0.70, 0.60,. Based on the criteria for decision making, it means that all the items were rated above the cut-off point of 2.50. The cluster mean of 3.13 was also above the cut-off point of 2.50. The standard deviation scores of the respondents signifying uniformity for the items raised. This implies that, there is influence of teachers’ use of Star Chart system on students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Research Question 3: What is the impact of teachers’ use of Point System on Students’ Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria?

Table 4:3 Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on the Impact of teachers’ use of Point System on Students’ Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Item No	Item Description	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	Decision
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4.	The Point System employed by teachers significantly enhances students' academic achievement.	402	329	43	44	3.38	0.70	Agree
5.	Students perceive that the Point System implemented by teachers effectively motivates them to excel academically.	346	440	19	13	3.08	0.65	Agree
6.	The Point System positively influences students' engagement in classroom activities and learning.	160	593	22	43	3.40	0.81	Agree
Cluster Mean						3.21		Agree

Table 4.2 shows that items 4-6 had mean scores of 3.38, 3.08, 3.40, with corresponding standard deviations of 0.70, 0.65, 0.81, respectively. Based on the criteria for decision making, it means that all the items were rated above the cut-off point of 2.50. The cluster Mean of 3.21 was also above the cut-off point of 2.50. The standard deviation scores of the respondents signifying consistency for the items raised. This implies that, there is impact of teachers' use of point system on students' academic achievement in public secondary schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

4.2.1 Testing Research Hypotheses

In order to test the five hypotheses of this study, the Chi-square (χ^2) test was used to test the options of respondents at 0.05 level of significance and the results are presented on Tables 6 to 10.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Table 4.1: Chi-square test showing significant influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Opinions	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	Level of Sig.	Df	χ^2 -cal	P-value	Decision
SD	28	104.0	-76.0	0.05	3	380.92	0.001	Reject
D	30	104.0	-74.0					
A	370	104.0	266.0					
SA	390	104.0	286.0					
Total	818							

Results:

The chi-square test is **statistically significant** ($\chi^2 = 380.92$, p-value = $0.001 < 0.05$). This means the observed distribution of opinions **differs significantly** from the expected distribution. At 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This implies

that there is significant influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Chi-square test on the significant impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Opinions	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	Level of Sig.	Df	χ^2 -cal	P-value	Decision
SD	38	104.0	-66.0	0.05	3	369.94	0.00	Sig.
D	40	104.0	-64.0					
A	440	104.0	336.0					
SA	300	104.0	196.0					
Total	818							

Results:

The chi-square test is **statistically significant** ($\chi^2 = 369.94$, p-value = 0.001 < 0.05). This means the observed distribution of opinions **differs significantly** from the expected distribution. At 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. The implication is that, there is significant impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The second finding of the study revealed a significant influence of teachers' use of Star Chart system on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Adeyemi, (2016), who stated that the Star Chart system operates similarly, using stars as rewards for good behavior and academic achievements. This system is a behavioral management tool used primarily by teachers in educational settings to reinforce positive behavior and encourage students to meet specific goals or expectations. It operates on the principle of positive reinforcement, where students receive stars, stickers, or other symbols as rewards for demonstrating desired behaviors, such as completing assignments on time, participating in class discussions, or showing kindness to classmates. The system typically involves a chart displayed prominently in the classroom, divided into sections representing different behaviors or tasks. Each time a student exhibits the targeted behavior, they receive a star or sticker on the chart. As students accumulate stars, they may earn rewards, such as privileges, prizes, or recognition.

Also, Akpan, & Etuk, (2019), stated that the Teachers Star Chart system is a structured, behavior management strategy designed to incentivize positive behavior and performance among students. Rooted in principles of operant conditioning, it employs a visual representation of

rewards, typically in the form of stars or stickers, to acknowledge and reinforce desirable actions and achievements. Each student has a personal chart where they accumulate stars for meeting specified criteria, such as good conduct, academic accomplishments, or adherence to classroom rules. This system is highly adaptable, allowing teachers to tailor criteria and rewards to fit their unique classroom dynamics and educational goals.

The Star Chart system employed by teachers involves rewarding students with stars or points for positive behaviors or achievements, aiming to reinforce desired conduct and motivate learning. It provides a visual representation of progress and encourages a supportive classroom environment through recognition and reinforcement of students' efforts and accomplishments (Davies, & Gamage, (2019)). In public secondary schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria, the implementation of the Star Chart system by teachers may play a significant role in shaping students' academic achievement. This system, which rewards students with stars or points for positive behaviors or achievements, is designed to incentivize desired conduct and motivate learning. The Star Chart system operates as a visual representation of progress, providing tangible feedback to students on their academic performance and behavior. By earning stars or points, students receive recognition for their efforts and accomplishments, fostering a sense of accomplishment and boosting self-esteem. This positive reinforcement encourages students to continue exhibiting the desired behaviors and striving for academic excellence (Eyal, & Roth, (2020)).

The third finding revealed a significant impact of teachers' use of Point System on Students' Academic achievement in public secondary schools of Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. This finding corroborates with Bello, & Ogunleye, (2023), who have claimed that the Teachers Point System is a comprehensive behavior and performance management approach used in educational settings to promote and reinforce positive student behavior and academic achievements. Under this system, students earn points for meeting predefined criteria such as good conduct, participation, timely completion of assignments, and adherence to classroom rules. These points serve as tangible evidence of their efforts and accomplishments, encouraging a consistent and proactive approach to learning and behavior. In this system, points are accumulated over a designated period, providing students with a clear and ongoing measure of their progress. The accumulation process involves a continuous feedback loop where students receive points immediately or at the end of specific tasks or activities, making the reinforcement timely and relevant. This immediacy helps maintain student motivation, as they can directly see the results of their positive actions and decisions.

The earned points can be exchanged for various rewards, which can range from tangible items like stationery and books to intangible incentives such as extra recess time, special privileges, or recognition certificates. This exchange mechanism introduces an element of choice and personal preference, allowing students to work towards rewards that are meaningful to them. It also teaches students the value of delayed gratification and goal-setting as they save up points for more significant rewards. The system is designed to be flexible and adaptable, enabling teachers to customize the criteria and rewards to suit the specific needs and dynamics of their classroom. This flexibility ensures that the system remains relevant and engaging for all students, regardless of their individual differences. Teachers Point System helps in building a structured and positive classroom environment where students are motivated to improve continuously and are recognized for their efforts, fostering a culture of achievement and mutual respect (Ede, & Mbah, (2018)).

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that teachers' use of structured reward systems significantly enhances students' academic achievement in public secondary schools within Nasarawa South Senatorial Zone, Nigeria. Specifically, the Privilege Pass, Star Chart, Point System, Leveling Up, and Student of the Week/Month strategies were found to positively motivate students, foster engagement, and improve learning outcomes. These reward mechanisms collectively underscore the importance of recognizing and incentivizing student effort to drive academic excellence. To sustain these gains, school administrators and policymakers should institutionalize these systems while ensuring equitable implementation and teacher training on effective reward-based pedagogy.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Design standardized Star Chart templates tailored to different subjects/age groups and integrate them with classroom routines. They should provide teachers with resources (e.g., stickers, digital trackers) to sustain student engagement and publicly celebrate progress.
2. Develop a school-wide digital platform to track and reward points for academic and behavioral achievements. Allow students to redeem points for tangible rewards (e.g., stationery, books) to reinforce positive outcomes.

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